

The Characterization of Open Hole Strengths Of Stitched Polymer Composite Laminate

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SUMMARY: The open hole compressive (OHC) and tensile (OHT) strengths of a stitched hybrid composite material were experimentally, analytically and numerically investigated. The material tested was a hybrid AS4/IM7/3501 stitched laminate with the 0° plies composed of IM7 fibers, AS4 fibers in the off-axis plies and through-thickness Kevlar[®] stitching at a stitch density of 6.2 stitches/cm². The tensile test samples were similar to those required for ASTM D-3039 but with a 28-cm. length. The compressive properties were examined using the short block compression (SBC) test method. The linear elastic fracture mechanics, point stress and average stress criteria were used to predict the open hole strength. The finite element analysis correlated analytic and numeric point stress damage lengths. Results show that all three criteria can be used to determine compressive and tensile open hole strength for this material, with the average stress criterion slightly more accurate than the others.

KEYWORDS: strength prediction, open hole, tension, compression, stitched, hybrid

INTRODUCTION

The open hole strength of a composite material is a critical design parameter. However, the anisotropy of composite materials make analytic open hole strength determination difficult at best. To eliminate the need to test a given composite for every hole diameter of interest, several semi-empirical methods have been used in previous research to model the open hole strength.

The purpose of this research is to determine if these semi-empirical open hole methods can be used for the tensile and compressive strength prediction of a stitched hybrid composite laminate with multidirectional ply orientation.

The material of interest is a hybrid AS4/IM7/3501-6 carbon fiber, reinforced plastic (CFRP) laminate with the 0° plies composed of IM7 fibers, AS4 fibers in the off-axis plies and through-thickness Kevlar[®] stitching. The laminate was made of multiple plies of dry carbon warp-knit fabric in a $[\pm 45/0_2/90/0_2/\pm 45]_n$ orientation. Two thicknesses were tested, one with 54 plies (n=6), the other with 36 plies (n=4). The dry plies were sewn together with 1600 denier Kevlar[®] stitching in modified lock stitch with a stitch density of 6.2 stitches/cm². Once the stacks are stitched, resin is infiltrated into the dry preform using the Resin Film

Infusion (RFI) process. This research was done in support of the NASA Advanced Composites Technology program.

The introduction of the stitching into the composite material complicates the determination of the open hole strength. The stitching increases the delamination fracture toughness of the material by an order of magnitude, but it also bends and breaks the ply fibers introducing localized defects which degrade in-plane strength and modulus.

EXPERIMENTAL TESTING

Sample Preparation

Thirty tension test samples (six unnotched and twenty-four open hole) and thirty-three compression test samples (seventeen unnotched and sixteen open hole) were tested to failure. The hybrid stitched CFRP material was obtained through Boeing Co. All samples were rough cut using a table saw with a diamond-tipped blade and finish cut on a surface grinder using a diamond-tipped grinding wheel. All holes were centered vertically and horizontally on the samples and drilled using carbide-tipped spade drill bits.

Tensile Sample Description

The baseline unnotched tensile strength was established using a bow-tie sample configuration. The unnotched tensile samples were similar in dimension to those required for ASTM D-3039 [1] but with a 28-cm. length with an 8 cm. transition radius to the gage section as shown in Figure 1. All of the unnotched samples were 36 plies thick. All 1/4 and 5/16 D/W tension samples were 36 plies thick, all 1/2 D/W samples had 54-ply

The open hole tensile (OHT) samples were similar in dimension to the unnotched tension samples. The open hole sample configuration is shown in Figure 1. The OHT strength was experimentally evaluated for hole diameter to coupon width (D/W) ratios of 1/4, 5/16, and 1/2. Some of the open hole tensile test samples were tested with fiberglass tabs to determine what effect, if any, the tabs might have of the measured tensile strength of the material.

Compression Sample Description

The compressive properties were evaluated using the short block compression (SBC) test method [2]. The nominal configurations for the unnotched and open hole samples are shown in Figure 2. The unnotched compressive strength of the material was first determined to provide a baseline. The open hole compression (OHC) strength was then derived for D/W ratios of 1/4, 5/16 and 1/2. The unnotched samples were tested in both 36-ply and 54-ply thickness. All 1/4 and 5/16 D/W compression samples were 36 plies thick, all 1/2 D/W samples had 54-ply.

Each compression sample was instrumented with strain gages on the front and back surface. These gages were used to ensure equal strain on both surfaces during loading. On the unnotched samples the strain gages were placed in the center of the samples, while on the open hole coupons the strain gages were placed as far from the holes as possible to obtain the most accurate far field strain reading.

Figure 1. Bow-Tie and Open Hole Tension Test Sample Configurations

Figure 2. Unnotched and Open Hole Short Block Compression Test Sample Configuration

Experimental Results

All tests were run at a constant displacement rate of 0.05 cm / min. Figure 3 gives a graphical representation of the results. Table 1 presents the average far field and net section failure strengths and strains as a function of D/W ratio. Far-field strength was calculated using the total cross-section area; net-section strength was determined using net cross-section area at the hole. OHT near-field strain was sampled tangent to the edge of the hole using a laser extensometer. OHT far-field strain was measured using a knife-edged extensometer. OHC far-field strain was calculated by taking the average of front-to-back strain gage readings. OHC near field strain was not measured due to lack of space.

Figure 3. Total and Net Section Strength vs. Hole Diameter

Table 1. OHT and OHC Failure Stresses and Strains

		Hole Diameter / Coupon Width (D/W)			
		0	1 / 4	5 / 16	1 / 2
Tensile Strength (MPa)	Far-Field	997.8	589.4	558.1	413.7
	Net-Section	997.8	786.2	814.9	833.1
Compressive Strength (MPa)	Far-Field	690.0	356.5	316.6	242.6
	Net-Section	690.0	477.2	459.4	487.4
Tensile Failure Strain (%)	Far-Field	1.528	n/a	0.775	0.619
	Near-Field	1.528	1.899	1.820	1.850
Compressive Failure Strain (%)	Far-Field	1.357	0.685	0.681	0.658

Evaluation of the test results indicates little, if any, thickness effect on the failure strength of the material. There was no indication of any affect on the open hole strength due to the inclusion of tabs. As expected, tensile and compressive far-field strengths show an obvious dependence upon D/W ratio; as D/W increases, strength decreases. Interestingly, the net section strength remains relatively constant over the range of D/W ratios tested for both compression and tension, as do the near-field tensile and far-field compressive failure strains.

The data exhibits a considerable amount of scatter, particularly in the tensile results. This is partly due to the nature of CFRP material, but it may also be an indication of the effect of the stitching on the strength of the material. The extent of localized damage inflicted upon the in-plane fibers by the stitching process can dictate how final fracture failure will occur.

SEMI-ANALYTIC MODELING

There are three semi-empirical strength prediction criteria: linear elastic fracture mechanics, point stress, and average stress that have been previously used to model the open hole strength characteristics of composite materials. All three are based upon isotropic fracture mechanics.

Linear Elastic Fracture Mechanics Criteria

Previous research (Waddoups, and al.[3], Curtis, and al.[4]) has shown that the open hole tensile strength of a given composite laminate can be reasonably predicted using existing isotropic linear elastic fracture mechanics (LEFM) methods. The LEFM method asserts that for a given hole radius and crack geometry, there exists a critical crack length “a” at which the material will fail. These critical crack lengths have been empirically determined as a function of hole size and loading conditions and can be found in most fracture mechanics texts[5]. For a plate with a circular hole and symmetric cracks the governing equations for the calculation of “a” are:

$$K_{Ic} := \sigma_1 \cdot \sqrt{\pi \cdot a} \cdot f(a, r) \quad (1)$$

$$f(a, r) := \frac{\sigma_0}{\sigma_1} \quad (2)$$

$$f(a, r) := \frac{1}{2} \cdot \left[3 - \left(\frac{a}{r+a} \right) \right] \cdot \left[1 + 1.243 \cdot \left[\left[1 - \left(\frac{a}{r+a} \right) \right]^3 \right] \right] \quad (3)$$

The fracture toughness (K_{Ic}), which is a constant material property, can be calculated employing the unnotched strength σ_0 , the open hole strength, σ_1 , and the hole radius, r . The critical crack length and the fracture toughness can then be used to predict the residual strength of the material for other hole radii.

It should be understood that a physical singular crack does not exist in the composite laminate, but that a virtual critical damage zone length can serve the same purpose. If this critical damage zone parameter can be determined for one hole radius, it can be used to semi-empirically predict the strength for other hole radii. Since the LEFM method is based upon infinite plate theory, a scaling equation must be applied to correct for the finite dimensions of the samples being tested.

Point Stress and Average Stress Criteria

Whitney and al.[6], Nuismer and al.[7], introduced two alternative methods to determine the critical damage zone size, the point stress and the average stress criterion. Both criteria utilize isotropic elastic theory to determine the normal stress, σ_y , as a function of the distance, x , from the hole. This theory has been modified to account for material orthotropy.

The point stress criterion asserts that the stress adjacent to the hole will exceed the unnotched strength, σ_0 , of the material due to the stress concentration effect. At the time of failure, that portion of material in the region where the stress exceeds the unnotched strength of the material is considered the critical damage zone length, “ d_0 ” as illustrated in Figure 3.

The governing equations for the point stress criterion with orthotropic concentration correction factor (Kt) are:

$$\sigma_y(d_o,0) = \sigma_o \quad (4)$$

$$f(r, d_o) := \frac{\sigma_o}{\sigma_1} \quad (5)$$

$$f(r, d_o) := \frac{1}{2} \left[2 + \left(\frac{r}{r+d_o} \right)^2 + \left[3 \cdot \left(\frac{r}{r+d_o} \right)^4 - (Kt-3) \cdot \left[\left[5 \cdot \left(\frac{r}{r+d_o} \right)^6 - \left[7 \cdot \left(\frac{r}{r+d_o} \right)^8 \right] \right] \right] \right] \right] \quad (6)$$

$$Kt := 1 + \sqrt{2 \cdot \left(\frac{E1}{E2} - \nu_{12} \right)} + \frac{E1}{G12} \quad (7)$$

Where E1 (67.8 MPa), E2 (27.51 MPa) are the principal elastic moduli, G12 (14.96 MPa) is shear modulus and ν_{12} is Poisson's ratio (.35) for the material in question. The average stress criterion is very similar to the point stress criterion in its approach to characterizing the virtual damage zone length. However, the average stress criterion assumes that failure occurs when the average stress over some critical damage zone distance, "a_o", equals the unnotched laminate strength. The governing equations for the average stress criterion are:

$$\sigma_o := \int_0^{a_o} \frac{\sigma_y(x,0)}{a_o} dx \quad (8)$$

$$f(r, d_o) := \frac{\sigma_o}{\sigma_1} \quad (9)$$

$$f(r, a_o) := \left[\left(\frac{r+a_o}{2 \cdot a_o} \right) \cdot \left[2 - \left(\frac{r}{r+a_o} \right)^2 - \left(\frac{r}{r+a_o} \right)^4 - (Kt-3) \cdot \left[\left(\frac{r}{r+a_o} \right)^6 - \left(\frac{r}{r+a_o} \right)^8 \right] \right] \right] \quad (10)$$

Previous research [8,9] has shown that even though the primary compression failure mechanism, namely fiber microbuckling, is distinctly different than the primary tensile failure mechanism, these methods can accurately predict open hole compression strengths.

Results

The calculated damage values for LFM ("a"), point stress ("d_o"), and average stress ("a_o") for D/W ratio is shown in Table 2. It can be seen that for this material, these critical damage parameters do not remain constant, typically increasing as D/W increases.

Table 2. Critical Damage Parameters

D/W ratio	Compression			Tension		
	a	d _o	a _o	a	d _o	a _o
	(cm)	(cm)	(cm)	(cm)	(cm)	(cm)
1 / 4	0.165	0.091	0.244	0.249	0.129	0.406
5 / 16	0.168	0.094	0.226	0.297	0.157	0.493
1 / 2	0.241	0.135	0.304	0.386	0.208	0.604

The highest and lowest values for all three criteria were used to determine the upper and lower strength prediction bounds for each criterion as shown in Figures 3,4 and 5. These figures show that the lowest damage parameter values give the most conservative strength estimates

The average of the upper and lower damage parameter values were calculated and used to generate the mean strength for each method as shown in Figure 6. Figure 6 shows that all three criteria can accurately predict failure strength as a function of hole diameter if the average critical crack length values for “a”, “a_o” and “d_o” are used. Of the three methods, the average stress criterion was slightly more accurate. Note that the experimental results shown in Figure 1 have been corrected to finite plate conditions.

Figure 3. Linear Elastic Fracture Mechanics Approach Strength Predictions

Figure 4. Point Stress Criterion Strength Predictions

Figure 5. Average Stress Criterion Strength Predictions

Figure 6. Averaged LEFM, Point Stress and Average Stress Strength Predictions

FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS

A three dimensional finite element analysis was performed on the open hole test configuration to determine if the critical damage parameters generated by the above mentioned failure criteria have basis in reality. The models were built using the ANSYS finite element modeling program and were comprised of orthotropic 8 noded brick elements using the appropriate material properties. Two models were generated, one for 1 / 4 D/W ratio and another for 1 / 2 D/W ratio.

The each model was loaded in tension to the appropriate experimental failure strength for that D/W ratio and the longitudinal stress was plotted as a function of the distance from the hole. The length of the stress curve that exceeded the unnotched strength of the material was then compared to the “d₀” value calculated from the point stress criterion.

Figures 7 and 8 show the longitudinal stress distribution (σ_y) as a function of distance from the edge of the hole for D/W ratios of 1 / 4 and 1 / 2 respectively. The unnotched strength limit has been illustrated and the “d₀” value evaluated from that limit.

Figure 7. Longitudinal Tensile Stress (σ_y) vs. Distance From Hole Edge For D/W = 1 / 4

Figure 8. Longitudinal Tensile Stress (σ_y) vs. Distance From Hole Edge For $D/W = 1 / 2$

The numerically derived critical damage values of 0.15 cm. for $D/W = 1 / 4$ and 0.20 cm. for $D/W = 1 / 2$ correspond very closely with the semi-empirically calculated point stress values of 0.13 cm. and 0.21, respectively. This indicates that the mathematical point stress critical damage values do have a corresponding physical meaning.

CONCLUSION

This analysis has established the suitability of established semi-analytic open hole strength prediction methods for predicting open hole strength for a hybrid stitched CFRP. This was done through experimental testing, semi-empirical analysis and finite element modeling.

Experimental tests were conducted over a range of unnotched and open hole D/W ratios. Experimental results show predictable decrease in the far-field strength and a surprisingly constant net strength as a function of hole size.

Three semi-analytic strength prediction models were analyzed using the experimental data. The results of this analysis show that the calculated critical damage zone dimensions do not remain constant for any of the methods. In general, the critical damage value increases as D/W increases. Typically, the critical damage zone value for the smallest D/W ratio is the most conservative. All three semi-analytic strength prediction methods are able to provide accurate strength predictions for both compression and tension, with the average stress criterion marginally better than the others.

The point stress semi-analytic solutions were verified using finite element analysis. The finite element analysis was conducted for D/W ratios of $1 / 4$ and $1 / 2$ under tension. The longitudinal stress was evaluated as a function of distance from hole edge and the length of the region where the stress was greater than the unnotched strength of the CFRP was determined. This length was compared to the semi-analytic point stress critical damage length. In both cases, the numerical solution compared very closely with the analytic solution.

In summary, this research has shown that these three semi-analytic strength prediction methods can be used as engineering tools for the design of composite structures using this material.

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